

TRANSVERSE MODULUS MEASUREMENT OF CARBON FIBRE BY ATOMIC FORCE MICROSCOPE AND NANOINDENTATION

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Objectives:

- Direct measurement of transverse Young's modulus E_T of carbon fibre through nano-scale indentation testing
- Study the influence from the surface damage induced by focused ion beam milling

Background

- Carbon fibre possesses high specific stiffness and strength
- Unknown transverse Young's modulus for carbon fibres (assumed to be low)

Methods

Flat surface on IMS65 was fabricated by focused ion beam (FIB). The potentially damaged layer was cleaned by low energy ion beam

Atomic force microscopy (AFM) and nanoindentation were employed to perform indentation testing, from which force-displacement curves were obtained

The indentation results were fitted by Hertz contact model and Oliver & Pharr model to extract the Young's modulus

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Conclusions:

- An amorphous damage layer, softer than the carbon fibre, exists
- After cleaning, the amorphous damage layer is removed. The transverse Young's modulus of IMS65 was found to be 26.5 GPa